

Development Issues of Tribal Population: A Study among Paniya and Kurichiya Tribal Communities

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Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: November

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2319-961X

Impact Factor: 4.005

Citation:

Sony Thilakan, K. T.
“Development Issues of Tribal Population: A Study among Paniya and Kurichiya Tribal Communities.” *Shanlax International Journal of Economics*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2018, pp. 32–35.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1488505>

Abstract

Kerala has achieved better level of development in many spheres, but there disparities in the development experience of different sections of the society especially among the tribal communities. The tribals in Kerala are in different stages of socio cultural and economic development. Most of them still depended on primary sector for their livelihood and they seem to remain in their traditional occupations. Out of the 36 tribal communities some have achieved better levels of development but others not. The Paniya and Kurichiya are the major tribal communities in Kerala. Kurichiyas are said to be wealthier and Paniyas are one of the poorest tribes in Kerala. There are differences in the level of education among them. Both of their major share of population reside at Wayanad district which also has the highest concentration of tribal people in Kerala. The main objective of the paper is to assess the factors responsible for the disparities in development among these two tribal communities in Wayanad district.

Introduction

The term development is used in a wider sense it means human development primarily and the main aim of development is to provide rising opportunities for for a better life. It is crucial to produce equitable distribution of income and wealth for promoting social justice and efficiency of production for the improvement of education health services housing etc.(Varghese, 2002) The concept of development consist of protecting human, social and ecological rights etc. It implies the removal of poverty, illiteracy, low economic opportunities, ill health, famine, absence of clean water, inadequate clothing and shelter, untouchability etc.

The state Kerala has achieved high social development. The achievements in the quality of life indicators is comparable to the highly developed nations. It could attain high adult literacy rate, life expectancy, low infant mortality rate and birth rate in spite of having low percapita GNP. The development experience of Kerala has received worldwide attention. The wealth and resources redistribution programmes by the state and participation in political programmes from the part of general public have gained the state a unique position in the development thinking. Even though the development experience of the state is unbalanced, the economic progress of the state might be derived from the rich sections of the societyand the poor sections still deprived of basic necessities like education health housing etc. The tribals are such community who remain far away the main stream society in in social and economic development. The impact of the process of development is slower among these communities and disparities are clearly visible when compared to the non-tribal people.

Tribal Development

Tribals in Kerala are the weaker sections of the society. They are still remain backward from the mainstream society. They preserve their traditional skills and knowledge. The tribal communities in Kerala differ each other in customs, language, economy, religion, beliefs etc. As compared to the main stream Kerala society they are backward in many respects like education, health, housing, occupation, income etc. Most of them are agriculture labourers they face various kinds of exploitation and live in poverty. After Independence many steps have been undertaken by the government and non-governmental organisations for their development. Since there is inequalities between the general people and tribals the main objective of tribal development is to alleviate these inequalities and develop them socially and economically. Tribal development aims to increase and strengthen the material aspects of tribal culture through better usage of the environmental resources that is agriculture, forest, flora and funa, minerals animal husbandry industrial potential and skills of the tribal people. The tribal development goals can be summarised in to long term objective and short term objective. The Long term objective aims to narrow down the gap between tribals and non tribals, improve the quality of their life. The short term objective aims to eliminate the exploitation by rapid soci economic development, improve organisational capabilities and building up inner strength of the tribals(Varghese, 2002).There are mainly five approaches for tribal development that is Political, administrative, religious, voluntary agencies and anthropological approaches.

Inspite of the high human development in Kerala the tribal communities live far away from the development process. They still face problems like extreme level of poverty, high level of social and developmental exclusion, low level of political economic and social empowerment, low level of access to empowerment, land alienation, low literacy and access to health care, depletion of social capital, deterioration of traditional knowledge, exploitation etc (Haseena,2006).

Tribals in Kerala

The tribal population in Kerala as per the 2011 Census is 4,84,839 which is 1.45 percent of the total population of the state out of this 4, 33,092 are in rural areas and 51,747 in urban areas. Kerala ranks first among the Indian states in respect of both female and male literacy among STs in India. There are 36 tribal communities in Kerala with unique characteristics. Each tribal community differ from another in many respects and the process of transformation among them is non-linear and non-homogeneous. The pace of the socio economic development differ from one another, some communities became more advanced and others have remained far behind. So it can be understood that there exist inter-community variation in the in the level of transformation.

The tribals in Kerala engage in various farming activities and many of them are agriculture labourers. The proportion of adivasi cultivators has declined since 1960s along with the increase in agriculture labour force. The percentage of cultivators in Kerala is much lower than that of all India level, reveals higher degree of landlessness among the adivasis in Kerala. The adivasi men and women engage in low skilled, low paid economic activities. Their also exist dual wage system in the adivasi region (Kerala Development Report, 2008).

The paniya and Kurichiyas are the major tribal communities in Kerala. They have diverse socio cultural economic status. From the social point of view Kurichiya community stand highest and Paniya community occupy the last strata of tribal hierarchy (Swamy 2011).

Paniya

Paniya comes from the word ‘pani’ meaning ‘work’. Therefore, Paniya means ‘one who works’. The Paniyas are agriculture labourers by tradition. They are experts in paddy cultivation. They have resemblance with the Negrito tribes having curly hair, thick lips and broad nose. They have strong muscular bodies which help them to do hard physical labour. Traditionally they were food gatherers and later they became bonded

labourers in agriculture sector. They started a settled life in the fringes of land provided by his master and did not own any land. The master's hire them in the vallurkavu festival on contract basis till the next festival comes. The Paniya families then move to the master's land. They got only subsistence income in return for their work. They got only food for work and food gathering were the major source of their livelihood. It was not sufficient to maintain his family so all the members of the family had to work in the master's land. The Paniya children could not attend schools since they also assist their parents. The Paniyas lived in a vicious circle of poverty. After the abolition of bonded labour system a few Paniyas got land under the Land Reforms act. Most of the land given to them were only 3 to 5 cents so it was only sufficient to build their houses. Only a few Paniyas have agricultural land. Since the literacy rate among them is very low they have to remain as agriculture labourers which is the job easily available to them locally. Their illiteracy and shyness forced them to rely on this locally available job.

The non-tribal settlers like Christians, Muslims, Nairs etc. directly influence the economy of Paniyas by controlling their occupations on whose land they are employed now a days for doing agriculture laboring. Since agriculture is seasonal in nature they have to remain unemployed for months, this is one of the major cause of poverty among them along with their drinking habit. Both men and women go for agriculture laboring.

The Paniyas usually migrate to nearby states especially to Coorg. They are hired through agents and they come to the Paniya colonies and hire them on contract basis and take them in jeeps to the destination. Both men and women migrate to Coorg. This is major source of income for the Paniya families.

Other communities consider them as lower community and ill treat them publically, so they feel a kind of inferiority complex and shyness. Dropout rate is high among the Paniyas. They do not give much importance to children's education. The Paniya children are still found to be reluctant to attend schools and engaging in various agriculture laboring activities. The Paniya community usually have a nature of extended family system with a sizable number of members and they live in colonies. Drinking habit is one of the evils that Paniyas facing today. Other communities consider them as lower community and ill treat them publically, so they feel a kind of inferiority complex and shyness.

Kurichiya

The Kurichiyas have a complex culture in their belief and rituals. They are very much efficient in archery. They were constituted to the army of Pazhassi Veera Varma Rajah in several battles against British force. They claim equal status with Brahmins and call themselves Malanamboothiries. They practice untouchability to all castes except Brahmins and reluctant take food with other castes except Nairs and Brahmins.

They mainly depended on agriculture, it is their principal economic activity. They practice co-operative farming. They have adopted settled cultivation with paddy. They cultivated paddy and ragi earlier their houses were situated near the paddy fields. At present they are engaged in cultivating banana, pepper, coffee etc. along with paddy cultivation. They are the first among the tribes started cash crop cultivation in Wayanad. They are said to be wealthier community.

They traditionally had extended family system and lived in 'Tharavadu' consisting so many families. The 'Karanavar' of the Tharavadu is vested with powers to control the members of the family. They adopted collective farming under the monitoring of Karanavar. All the family members engage in cultivation so they did not have to depend on outside labour for cultivation. The Kurichiya men engage in the ploughing and women, planting and weeding.

It is considered as their traditional occupation. Some of the members had gone to work in plantation sector during the colonial period along with their practice of cultivation. The Kurichiyas were traditionally land owners. There were acres of land under the Tharavadu. But today they follow nuclear family system with separate houses. As a land owning class they lead a comparatively better standard of living. Since the Kurichiyas were experts in archery hunting was another major economic activity of them along with cattle

rearing. Most of the Kurichiyas lost their lands today due to the invasion of settlers from the plains. Many of the Kurichiya got jobs in the Government departments. The younger generation is more educationally advanced and some of them have gone to other white collar jobs.

Cocclusion

The Paniyas and Kurichiyas stand in two extremes of socio economic development. Even though the state undertake so many development initiatives, the disparities in land holdings, type of occupation they follow, educational attainment and attitude towards education, the place of their habitat (colony), attitude toward progress, drinking habit, informational asymmetry are the major factors that led to the socio economic differences among these tribal communities.

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